

DEVELOPMENT OF ANTI-CORROSION COATING SOLUTION USING SURFACE MODIFIED METAL NANOPARTICLES FOR STEEL SHEET

J. Choi¹, E. Kang¹, H. B. Byun¹, C. Choi², S. E. Shim^{1*}

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, Inha University, Incheon, South Korea,

² Surface Technology Research Group, POSCO, Gwangyang, South Korea

* Corresponding author (seshim@inha.ac.kr)

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1 Introduction

There is an issue related to environment which the steel industry cannot ignore. Conventionally, steel sheet is modified by chromate conversion coating, and when it is disposed or recycled, it releases hexavalent chromium [1]. The hexavalent chromium is toxic and causes water and air pollution.

Because of this problem, an alternative using silicone resin or fluorine resin as coating solution has been suggested. Although this also has the limitation to use because polymeric resin coating has to be formed with 20 - 30 μm thickness which makes steel sheet poor at electrical conductivity and causes high production cost, it has been widely used in consumer electronics decoration [2].

Herein, with an aim to solve this problem, a resin layer including conductive metal nanoparticles was prepared on the surface of a galvanized steel sheet to give erosion resistance and electrical conductivity. In order to disperse 100 nm-sized various metal nanoparticles with high specific gravity and strong van der Waals force arising from the great surface area, the metal nanoparticles were surface-modified by PEG through chemical reaction. By this approach, the improved dispersion stability of metal nanoparticles in aqueous binder solution was achieved and corresponding conductivity and anti-corrosion capability were successfully obtained.

2 Experimental

2.1 Grafting of Polyethylene Glycol (PEG)

3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES), polyethylene glycol (PEG, Mw = 600 g/mol) having terminal carboxylic acid were purchased from Shin-Etsu Silicones and Fluka, respectively. Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn nanoparticles with an approximate average diameter of 100 nm were purchased from NTbase, S. Korea. Polyurethane (PU)-based aqueous anti-fingerprint coating solution with 50 % solid content

(Bumwoo Chemical Co., Ltd.) was used as a coating binder.

In order to disperse the metal nanoparticles in aqueous PU binder solution, the following chemical reaction to graft water-soluble PEG chains was conducted. The grafted PEG chains improve the colloidal dispersion stability of the metal nanoparticles in PU binder solution due to steric hindrance and electrostatic repulsion.

In Scheme 1, APTES and carboxylic acid-terminated PEG were added in a 500 ml three necked flask and stirred at 60 °C for 24 hrs and mixed with 600 ml ethanol [3]. Metal nanoparticles were added to the APTES-terminated PEG for surface modification. Then, the excess ethoxy groups were changed to hydroxyl group by hydrolysis reaction. After that, the resultant was washed with ethanol in an aspirator 5 - 6 times and dried in a 60 °C oven [4].

The surface-modified metal nanoparticles were added to aqueous PU coating solution. The metal nanoparticle concentration to anti-fingerprint solution was 1 phr. The solution was ultrasonicated at 350 W for 10 min.

2.2 Coating Steel Sheet and Performance Test

A steel sheet was treated with acetone to remove impurities, washed with water, and dried. The anti-fingerprint coating solution containing modified metal nanoparticles was spread with #5 bar coater. It was dried at 180 °C in an induction heating furnace. After that, the sample sheet was tested for electrical conductivity and erosion resistance with salt spray tester for 2 cycles. For salt spray test (SST), brine was sprayed (1.5 ml/hr) for 8 hrs, and stopped for 16 hrs.

2.3 Characterization

Turbiscan (Formulaction, France) was used to evaluate dispersion stability of metal nanoparticles in aqueous coating solution. FT-IR (Bio-Red FTS135) was used to detect PEG molecules attached

to metal nanoparticles. The atoms attached to metal nanoparticles were analyzed by EDX (Hitachi S-4300). Electrical conductivity of steel sheet which containing metal nanoparticles (Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn) in anti-fingerprint coating layer was measured by Loresta-GP MCP-T600, Mitsubishi Chemical Corps., Japan.

3 Result and Discussion

3.1 Surface Modification of Metal Nanoparticles

Fig. 1 shows the morphology of various metal nanoparticles used in this study. The nanoparticles produced by electrical explosion of wire have the purity higher than 99.99% and the morphology of aggregates of spherical primary particles. The average particle size of Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn was all about 100 nm. Since Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn nanoparticles have a very high specific gravity such as 2.7 (Al), 7.13 (Zn), 7.27 (Sn), and 8.93 (Cu), it is difficult to disperse these metal particles in aqueous solution. This is why the surface modification of metal nanoparticles is necessary to overcome these great specific gravity and van der Waals force among the metal nanoparticles.

Fig.1. SEM morphology of various metal nanoparticles used in this study; (a) Al, (b) Cu, (c) Sn, and (d) Zn (scale bar: 1 μm).

PEG diacid was used to endow the dispersion stability to metal nanoparticles. First, amine groups on APTES were reacted with carboxylic acid groups on PEG diacid by a simple condensation reaction. Metal nanoparticles were added to the APTES-terminated PEG for surface modification. Then, the excess ethoxy groups were changed to hydroxyl group by hydrolysis reaction (Scheme 1).

Throughout this simple procedure, hydrophilic PEG chains were chemically grafted onto metal nanoparticles to improve the dispersion stability via steric hindrance. In addition, the terminal carboxylic acid loses proton to form carboxylic anion (COO⁻) in water, which further enhances the dispersion stability of metal particles via electrostatic repulsion. The combined stabilization by steric hindrance and electrostatic repulsion significantly improves the colloidal stability of metal nanoparticles in anti-fingerprint coating solution, preventing the agglomeration and sedimentation of metal particles.

Scheme.1. Surface modification of metal nanoparticles using PEG

FT-IR spectra in Fig. 2. confirm the successful surface modification of metal nanoparticles via surface-grafting of PEG. The peak at 560 cm⁻¹ indicates the bond between metal and oxygen. The peaks around 1111 and 1049 cm⁻¹ suggest the existence of Si-O-H and Si-O-Si, respectively. The 2 broad bands around 3419 and 1628 cm⁻¹ are related to N-H stretching vibration and NH₂ stretching, respectively. The grafting of PEG appears at 1736 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 2886 cm⁻¹ (C-H), at 1111 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C) [5].

Fig.2. FT-IR spectra of PEG-grafted metal nanoparticles.

For further investigation, EDX analysis was used. As can be seen from Scheme 1, the PEG-grafted metal nanoparticles should have primary atoms of C, O, and Si. EDX data in Table 1 proves the result.

Table 1. EDX data of PEG-grafted metal nanoparticles.

Elem.	Al	Cu	Sn	Zn
	At. %	At. %	At. %	At. %
C	60.02	40.62	83.03	33.84
O	19.88	32.63	14.08	37.4
Al	19.96	0	0	0
Cu	0	22.08	0	0
Sn	0	0	2.88	0
Zn	0	0	0	28.43
Si	0.13	0.38	0.01	0.33
N	0	4.3	0	0
Total	100	100	100	100

3.2 Dispersion Stability in Coating Solution

The dispersion stability in coating solution containing metal nanoparticles was monitored by measuring the backscattering and transmission of monochromatic light ($\lambda = 880 \text{ nm}$) from the suspension. Suspension in a glass tube was placed in the instrument and the transmission of light from suspensions was then periodically measured along the height at room temperature. The transmission detector receives the light going out of the sample at 0° from the incident beam, while the backscattering detector receives the light scattered by the sample at 135° from the incident beam. The backscattering (BS) and transmittance (T) of incident light are measured by calculating transport mean free path of photons (l^*) throughout the medium [6];

$$BS \approx (1/l^*)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$T \approx \exp(-r/l) \quad (2)$$

where r is an internal radius of a measurement cell. The photon transport mean free path (l^*) and photon mean free path (l) are defined;

$$l^* = \frac{2d}{3\Phi(1-g)Q_s} \quad (3)$$

$$l = \frac{2d}{2\Phi Q_s} \quad (4)$$

where d , Φ , g , and Q_s denote a particle mean diameter, the volume fraction of a dispersed phase, asymmetry factor, and scattering efficiency factor, respectively.

Raw and PEG-grafted metal nanoparticles were dispersed in PU binder solution via sonication before analysis. The results are shown in Fig. 3. Y-axis represents the change of backscattering caused by sedimentation of metal nanoparticles and X-axis denotes the height of the sample cell from bottom to top. The change of backscattering in Y-axis suggests the sedimentation of metal nanoparticles. The dispersion stability of Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn nanoparticles was significantly improved by surface-modification using PEG. Especially, Cu shows the best dispersion stability. However, most raw metal nanoparticles were precipitated after 3 days due to its huge specific gravity and attractive force among the nanoparticles.

Fig.3. Dispersion stability of raw and PEG-grafted metal nanoparticles in coating solution: (a) Al, (b) Cu, (c) Sn, and (d) Zn.

3.3 Evaluation of Corrosion Resistance

Corrosion resistance test was performed to the galvanized steel sheets coated with Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn metal nanoparticles-embedded coating layer. The results present that Sn, Al, and Zn metal nanoparticles resist to corrosion, whereas the sample containing Cu nanoparticles is vulnerable to corrosion attack (Fig. 4). The corrosion of Fe covered the whole surface of the sample steel sheet.

Fig.4. Corrosion test of steel sheets coated with PU anti-fingerprint solution containing various metal nanoparticles: (a) none (PU binder) (b) Sn, (c) Al, (d) Zn, and (e) Cu.

The tendency of corrosion resistance can be explained via electrochemical reaction. Corrosion process follows the equation below.

In order for corrosion to take place, metal has to be ionized first. When metal loses electron, oxidized metal ions make a bond with hydroxide ions and it leads to metal corrosion. In this process, the oxidation tendency is explained by electromotive force (Emf) in Table 2. The metal with high Emf is more oxidizable than metal with lower Emf.

Table 2. Series of electromotive force (Emf).

Electrode Reaction	Standard Potential, ϕ° , in volts at 25 °C
$Cu \rightarrow Cu^{2+} + 2e^{-}$	-0.342 V
$Zn \rightarrow Zn^{2+} + 2e^{-}$	0.763 V
$Fe \rightarrow Fe^{2+} + 2e^{-}$	0.440 V
$Sn \rightarrow Sn^{2+} + 2e^{-}$	0.136 V
$Al \rightarrow Al^{3+} + 3e^{-}$	1.66V

In this study, PU-coated sample sheets consist of three layers (Scheme 2); Fe, Zn, and PU coating layer. Zn was plated on Fe layer, and the solution coating layer was formed on the Zn layer. Although each layer cannot perfectly protect Fe from the air, Zn efficiently protects Fe from corrosion via electrochemical reaction. Zn has strong oxidation

tendency compared to Fe. Zinc oxidizes first to give electrons to iron so that iron sheet is protected electrochemically [7].

Scheme 2. Cross section of (a) galvanized steel sheet and (b) galvanized steel sheet coated with PU binder containing metal nanoparticles.

In case of steel sheets coated with PU binder containing metal nanoparticles (Scheme 2), metal nanoparticles exist in PU coating layer and the type of metal influences corrosion according to its oxidation tendency. The metal nanoparticles are mixed homogeneously in coating layer and contact with air and zinc, therefore, the type of metal nanoparticles determines the corrosion resistance. For example, Al nanoparticles in PU layer tends to oxidize first because Al has higher Emf than Zn and Fe. Therefore, Zn and Fe are protected by Al oxidation. However, for Cu nanoparticles-embedded coating layer, Zn oxidizes first. Since Fe has higher Emf than Cu, Fe also oxidizes and Cu is reduced. Therefore, Cu-incorporated coating shows red rust of Fe throughout the entire steel sheet.

3.4 Electrical Conductivity of Coated Steel Sheet

Electrical conductivity is important for polymer-coated steel sheet for subsequent processing such as welding. Therefore, proper electrical conductivity should be guaranteed. Electrical conductivity of steel sheet coated with PU layer containing various metal nanoparticles (Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn) are given in Table 3. In case of PU binder containing no metal particles, the electrical resistance was not measureable due to its huge resistance. However, electrical resistance was significantly reduced for PU binder containing metal nanoparticles. Reduced

electrical resistance of steel sheets coated with the PU layer containing Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn was similar in the range of $0.0332 - 0.060 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}\Omega$.

Table 3. Electrical resistance of coated steel sheet by PU binder containing various metal nanoparticles and maximum coating quantity

Metal nanoparticles	Electrical resistance ($10^{-3} \text{ m}\Omega$)	Maximum coating quantity (mg/m^2)
None (PU binder)	N/A	N/A
Al	0.0340~0.060	2000
Cu	0.0335~0.059	2400
Sn	0.0332~0.052	1700
Zn	0.0337~0.058	1900

4 Conclusion

In order to endow electrical conductivity and corrosion resistance to resin-coated galvanized steel sheet, various metal nanoparticles (Al, Cu, Sn, and Zn) were incorporated into PU binder solution. To do so, metal nanoparticles were first surface-modified with hydrophilic PEG molecules by chemical reaction using amino-group bearing silane coupling agent (APTES). The surface modification was confirmed by means of FT-IR and EDX analysis. The PEG-modified metal nanoparticles show much enhanced dispersion stability in aqueous PU coating solution as analyzed by Turbiscan. The PU coating solution containing modified metal nanoparticles were coated on galvanized steel sheet and corrosion test was performed. The result shows Al, Sn, and Zn nanoparticles maintains good corrosion resistance. However, Cu nanoparticles cause severe corrosion of Fe. The tendency of corrosion follows the Emf of oxidation reaction of metals. Finally, the electrical conductivity was improved due to the presence of metal nanoparticles in insulating PU coating layer.

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